

TEACHING LANGUAGE PHENOMENA THROUGH TEXT ANALYSIS ON THE BASIS OF ANTHROPOCENTRIC APPROACH

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Abstract: in this article, through text analysis, the development of speech, linguistic, pragmatic competence in students and the inculcation of national values on this basis, the anthropocentric approach has great potential in the inculcation of national values, the issues of completing tasks that help to form the ability to read and understand the text are highlighted.

Key words: text, national value, anthropocentric approach, reading comprehension, text analysis, tasks.

Enter. The formation of the anthropocentric paradigm is connected with the research of the factor of the person who owns the language - the speaker. The emergence of the anthropocentric turn in linguistics put aside the principle of structuralism of language research "in and for itself" and focused on the individual factor. At the same time, the anthropocentric approach to language is increasingly consolidating its status as an independent paradigm, incorporating the latest advances in these fields.

Literature analysis. In Uzbek linguistics, there is a certain amount of research devoted to the study of the problems of the anthropocentric approach to language. In particular, famous linguists V.A. Maslova ¹ and N. Mahmudov ² say that the roots of anthropocentrism, which is currently recognized as one of the leading paradigms of linguistics, were nourished by the theoretical views of V. Von Humboldt and L. Weissgerber. The general methodological basis of the subject is made up of the teachings that have been studied since antiquity. In particular, Aristotle, A. Potebnya, V.A. Maslova, J. Lakoff, A.P. Chudinov, A. Baranov, A.R. Luria, A.V. Malinka ³; in Uzbek linguistics, A. Shomaksudov, H. Abdurahmonov, N. Mahmudov, M. Mirtoji, M. Mukarramov, S. Usmonov, A. Haji, S. Rahmatulla, E. Begmatov, N. Mahmudov, A. S. Omasudov, I. Rasulov, R. Kong'urov, S. Karimov and other scientists' theoretical views are among them. A.A. Ufimseva, V.G. Gak, Y.S. Kubryakova and D. Khudayberganova's ⁴ scientific conclusions form the theoretical basis of the research. Subject to know process his nomination

¹ Maslova V.A. Linguistic culture. - Moscow: Academy, 2001. - S. 170; <http://ph.ras.ru/elib0215.html>: New Philosophical Encyclopedia.

² Mahmudov N. Searching for ways of perfect study of the language... // Uzbek language and literature. - Tashkent, 2012. - No. 5. - P. 3-16.

³ Malinka A.V., Nagel O.V. Lexical nomination: onomasiological and cognitive approach. - Moscow: Smysl; Academy, 2004. - S. 45.

⁴ Khudayberganova D.S. Anthropocentric research of artistic texts in Uzbek language: Filol.fan.dok-ri...diss. autoref. - Tashkent, 2015.

with dependent _ be , of the sign surface coming with will pass Meaning anthropocentric characteristic in itself _ _ a person nature features reflection makes _ Researchers N. Z. Normurodova ⁵, ⁶, Sh. T. Makhmaraimova ⁷, GNNasrullayeva in their research⁸ Uzbek in linguistics metaphor anthropocentric in the interpretation explanation necessity and metaphors in the classification anthropocentric interpretation , cognitive and conceptual a metaphor classification circle thoughts , Sobirova in research ⁹- ¹⁰- ¹¹- ¹²- ¹³-¹⁴ mother language to education anthropocentric approaches discussion will be done .

Research methodology. The article discusses the issues of teaching language phenomena based on an anthropocentric approach. It describes the development of students' speech, linguistic, and pragmatic competence through text analysis. The anthropocentric approach has great potential in inculcating national values, and issues of performing tasks that help to form the ability to read and understand the text are studied.

Analyzes and results. The analyzes showed that in the second half of the 20th century and the first decades of the 19th century, metaphorical processes were studied in 3 main directions (traditional, system-structural and anthropocentric) and 8 aspects in

⁵ Normurodova NZ Linguistic development of anthropocentrism in English artistic discourse. Doctor of Philology... diss. author. - Tashkent, 2020.

⁶ Normurodova NZ Anthropocentric study of Uzbek language metaphors (nominative aspect). Monograph. – Termiz: Surkhannashr, 2020. – 214 p.

⁷ Makhmaraimova Sh.T. Cognitive aspect of theomorphic metaphors in the national linguistic image of the world. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)... diss. – Against, 2018.

⁸ Nasrullayeva G. Linguistic, communicative, pragmatic aspect of anthropocentric metaphor. Phil.science.b . doctor of philosophy (PhD) ... diss. autoref. – Against, 2018.

⁹ Sobirova M. The use of integrated technology in teaching of humanism in language education. POLISH SCIENCE JOURNAL (ISSUE 1(34) - Warsaw: Sp. z oo " iScience ", 2021. Part 3 – 234 p. <https://sciencecentrum.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/POLISH%20SCIENCE%20JOURNAL%20%E2%84%9634%20-%203%20%28web%29.pdf> str . 98-105

¹⁰ Sobirova M. I n imparting humane education use of integrated technology . In Volume 8, Issue 1, of JournalNX -A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, ISSN No: 2581 – 4230. Impact factor 8.155. VOLUME 8, ISSUE 1, January 2022, Published by Novateur Publication, MS India. - P. 151-158. <https://repo.journalnx.com/index.php/nx/article/view/3880/3718>

¹¹ Sobirova M. Innovative Technologies of Teaching in the Field of Higher Education Techniques. [Design Engineering](http://thedesigengineering.com/index.php/DE/issue/view/31) . International Research Journal of Advanced Engineering and Science (IRJAES) SCOPUS 5288-5295 <http://thedesigengineering.com/index.php/DE/issue/view/31> .

¹² Sobirova M. I n imparting humane education use of integrated technology . In Volume 8, Issue 1, of JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, ISSN No: 2581 – 4230. Impact factor 7 . 2 . VOLU - ME 8, ISSUE 1, January 2022, Published by Novateur Publication , MS India. - P. 151-158. <https://repo.journalnx.com/index.php/nx/article/view/3880/3718>

¹³ Sobirova M. Anthropocentric approach to language. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 07 (111), <http://t-science.org/axivDOI/2022/07-111.html> - P. 36-39.

¹⁴ Sobirova M. **Teaching language phenomena on the basis of anthropocentric approach.** <https://www.int-jecse.net/abstract.php?id=5377> International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education (INT-JECSE) OI:10.9756/INTJECSE /V14I7.91 ISSN: 1308-5581 Vol 14, Issue 07 2022 .

Uzbek linguistics. These are studied: semasiological, lexicological, stylistic, system-structural, anthropocentric direction (in particular, on the basis of cognitive, linguocultural, sociopsycholinguistic, pragmatic approach) and lexicographic aspect.

Anthropocentric ideas to Uzbek linguistics from a scientific point of view literally correct, a linguist who has deeply understood the essence scientist D.Khudaiberganova is in line with the ideas of modern metaphorology emphasizes the anthropocentric nature of the metaphor.

The organization of the teacher training process in higher education institutions, the state of qualified pedagogical practice, our observations and the analysis of our school experiences show that, based on the new demands of the times, education, in particular, mother tongue education, is today the world's the possibilities of teaching anthropocentric linguistics, formed as an independent scientific paradigm in linguistics education, based on modern approaches, are not covered. Based on the requirements of scientific and technical development, there is a need to develop and implement the principles and technologies of the anthropocentric approach in mother tongue education.

in the sense of ¹⁵possessor, possessor, and the mechanism of human linguistic activity is related to the linguistic consciousness, mentality, and speech situation of the person who owns the language. requires learning in dependence. If the word *sahib* comes in the meaning of mastering a skill, then when we say a master of a language, we also understand a professional who has mastered the science of language, knows the qualities and characteristics of the language perfectly, and has been able to bring it to the level of art.

A scientific paradigm (from the Greek "example, model") is directed to the study of the object of science, its theoretical concepts that prevailed in a certain period and, on this basis, is similar in different departments of science, and is interconnected. is a set of specific research methods. Unlike scientific methodology and scientific methods, it has a clear historical character and a limit of socio-cultural distribution. This term was introduced in 1962 in the famous work "Structure of Scientific Revolutions" by the American philosopher and historian T.Kun.

The anthropocentric paradigm is the change and orientation of researchers' interests from the object to the subject, that is, the analysis of man in language, and language in man. In the words of IABoudin de Courtenay, "Language exists only in the individual brains, minds, and psyches of the individuals who make up the language community."

"Methodology of mother tongue teaching" is considered a pedagogical science, but its scientific basis is linguistics. Every scientific achievement in the field of linguistics undoubtedly affects the content of the mother tongue course; when necessary, it creates the need to update it.

Language is a great blessing, a powerful force that has built not only a person, but also a human society, caused its development, and connects different countries even now. Therefore, great attention has always been paid to the issues of language learning, the development of the most effective intensive methods of language education, language teaching methods and approaches to teaching have been regularly improved.

¹⁵ An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. Five volumes. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan. 2020.

One of the main factors of achieving the final goal in teaching the mother tongue is the development of students' speech, linguistic, pragmatic competence through text analysis and inculcating national values on this basis. The anthropocentric approach is notable for its great potential in inculcating national values¹⁶. Based on the purpose of language teaching, the use of humanistic artistic texts as teaching materials, reading and understanding through them, expressive reading, retelling of what you have read and understood, text analysis, emotional coloring of the impressions you get from the text. Possession of oral and written expression skills by means of providing linguistic units shows the level of students' knowledge.

Worked with 6-8 texts during one academic year the reader is a conscious perception of information in any style get to the qualification being goes"¹⁷.

Indeed, the reader in the text expressed of words compare the dictionary meaning and the meaning in the context, pay close attention to his logical thinking, extract the most important from the information, make his own conclusions about the text must have the ability to give. In this process students not only native language, but any science, correctly read and understand the texts and learned from them to present their information orally and in writing by reading to understand qualification¹⁸ can be developed.

Below is a task that helps build reading comprehension skills some are recommended:
assignment

Look at the old man allowance not worth it money was _ But every month the postman is a woman arm league **more** money arrested would go

The simple woman did not know that the child of that woman would give it to the postman.

"Ca n't you give the money to mother with your own hands?" I asked. To this question, he answered: "I will give my mother as much money as she needs, and I will not ask where they spent the money I gave to them so that they would not be burdened. I increased her allowance several times from my own account so that she could use it freely. I ask them not to use the money given to them as "my child's money."

Questions about the given text:

1. Which of the following would you choose as a heading for your text and why?

Written answer give _

1. A small allowance
2. Own money calm down to use
3. Pension increase
4. The child's humanity

2. "Nice the old man." allowance not worth it money was _ But every month the postman is a woman arm league more money arrested would go A simple woman did not know that the child

¹⁶ Sobirova M. Mother tongue teaching based on the anthropocentric approach. Monograph. - Namangan: Arjumand media. 2022 - B.175.

¹⁷ Mavlonova K. Formation of students' reading comprehension skills. Global education and development of national methodology. Proceedings of the Republican scientific-practical conference. - Tashkent, 2020. - P.149-150.

¹⁸ Sobirova M. Anthropocentric approach based on teacher _ activities development. "Pedagogy" magazine. 2022 No 4. - B. 19 - 24.

of that woman would give it to the postman. Why do you think the woman did not know that the allowance was high?

3. "Ca n't you give the money to your mother with your own hands?" I asked. He could have given this money to his mother. What do you think? Is the child doing the right thing?

4. Different shown pay attention to the words giveOf them how many typo?

5. " I increased her allowance several times from my own account so that she could use it freely and without embarrassment. I tell them not to use the money given to them as `my child's money. ' 'lats manifestation happening?

6. What are you going to do to increase your money in the future?

7. What would you do for your mother if you had more money?

8. Do you think that the path taken by the humanitarian guy above is the right one? What other things can mothers do?

Conclusions. Language skills are in all areas of human life since it is important to analyze the texts with educational content as above with an anthropocentric approach, the students should read the texts correctly to understand and of these received information Developing oral and written communication skills is extremely important in today's increasingly global challenges.

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